

Retention of ^{80m}Br in (n,γ) Irradiated Bromates. Part III. Calcium Bromate Crystals

H. J. Arnikar, D. K. Sharma* and S. F. Patil

The thermal annealing of bond ruptures caused by (n, γ) reaction in hydrated and dehydrated forms of the calcium bromate is studied. The rate and extent of annealing are found to be almost same in both the forms of calcium bromate crystals. The annealing reactions are found to obey a formal first order rate law with an activation energy of 2.7 kcal.

Chemical transformations of the recoil bromine in bromates following thermal neutron capture and the subsequent effects due to annealing by heat or radiations have been studied extensively¹⁻⁷. Recent work of Mohanty and Khare⁸ on γ -irradiated calcium bromate as well as our earlier work on (n, γ) irradiated hydrated cadmium bromate⁹ has shown that phase transformation occurring during annealing due to loss of water of crystallization induces a rapid recombination of the ruptured fragments and this process virtually ceases once the phase transformation is complete.

In continuation of our earlier work we report here results of our study on the annealing characteristics of ^{80m}Br and its kinetics in dehydrated and hydrated calcium bromate and the effect thereon of structural rearrangements due to phase transformation. A comparison of the results with those due to γ -irradiation in the same system would be helpful to an understanding of the mechanism of retention in these systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

Calcium bromate was synthesized by boiling the slurry of calcium sulphate and excess of barium bromate for about 8 hrs. After the removal of barium sulphate by filtration, the less soluble barium bromate was separated by concentrating the solution containing calcium bromate. The crude product was allowed to crystallize. This was dissolved in a minimum quantity of water and kept overnight at -20° at which temperature the solubility of barium bromate is only about 0.02%. The subsequent purification of the calcium bromate was carried out by two crystallizations using distilled water.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, University of Manchester, Manchester-13, U.K.

1. G. Harbottle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 805.
2. I. G. Campbell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **15**, 46.
3. T. Andersen and A. C. Maddock, *Radiochim. Acta.*, 1963, **1**, 220.
4. T. Andersen, H. E. Lundager and K. Olesen, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 2409.
5. G. E. Boyd and Q. V. Larson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 254.
6. J. W. Cobble and G. E. Boyd, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1282.
7. A. G. Maddock and H. Müller, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 509.
8. S. R. Mohanty and M. Khare, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 853.
9. H. J. Arnikar, D. K. Sharma and S. F. Patil, *Radiochim. Acta.*, 1970, **13**, 164.

4 g of purified calcium bromate were irradiated with a 13 curie $^{124}\text{Sb}(+\text{Be})$ photo-neutron source in a boron-free soft glass tube for 18 hrs. at room temperature and subsequently subjected to heating in an oil bath at various temperatures and for different periods. The temperature of the oil bath was maintained to within $\pm 1^\circ$ by an electronic control. Experiments on the dehydrated calcium bromate were carried out by dehydrating the calcium bromate $[\text{Ca}(\text{BrO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ at 150° for 2 hrs, and sealing the samples under vacuum before irradiation.

The experiments at -196° were performed by irradiating the samples in soft glass tubes kept in a vacuum flask containing liquid nitrogen which was replenished from time to time.

Chemical separation : Annealed samples were subjected to chemical analysis using the method described earlier⁹ which depends on the rapid exchange between bromine and its oxy-ions of all oxidation states, except the bromate, produced during irradiation.

Activity measurement is done as described earlier⁹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the variation of percentage retention of ^{80m}Br in hydrated and dehydrated calcium bromate with the time of annealing at different temperatures. The values of the retentions used in Fig. 1 are the mean of two or more independent determinations in each case. The results are summarised below :

- (1) The retention of ^{80m}Br at room temperature for the hydrated and dehydrated forms is about the same being 18–19%.
- (2) The effect of residual air in the sealed tube does not appear to have any marked effect on retention, as shown by the same value of retention observed in hydrated calcium bromate sealed in vacuum or in air.

- (3) The annealing reactions in the hydrated and dehydrated calcium bromate crystals are fast in the beginning but slow down later giving a constant value of retention for each temperature.
- (4) The rate and the extent of annealing are almost the same at all the temperatures in both the systems (Fig. 1).
- (5) ΔR_0 , the increase in percentage retention, changes linearly with $1/T$ (Fig. 2).
- (6) The retention decreases to about 15% in hydrated calcium bromate if the irradiation is carried out at liquid nitrogen temperature.
- (7) Irradiation of the solution of calcium bromate gave a retention of 17% which was found to be independent of concentration over a range of 0.3 to 1.5 *M*.

The recoil energy following (n, γ) event generally exceeds the lattice energy of the crystal, resulting in a finite separation of recoil species. Only a limited combination of these fragments would be possible at room temperature due to the energy barrier of recombination reactions for the trapped fragments. Assuming a Boltzmann distribution of energy for the fragments, the fraction n/n_0 possessing energy $\geq E$ (the barrier value) at temperature T , is given by $n/n_0 = e^{-E/kT}$. During thermal annealing at increasing temperatures, the necessary energy is provided to increasing fractions of the recoil fragments to overcome the energy barrier thereby resulting in a greater proportion of the reformation of these fragments to form parent molecules. It is seen from Fig. 1 that the annealing reactions are fast in the beginning and saturate in the end at every temperature. It is not, however, possible to study the latter process because of the short life of ^{80m}Br .

The retention value of about 18%, observed in the present work for ^{80m}Br in dehydrated and hydrated calcium bromate, agrees very well with the values reported earlier for ^{82}Br in the same system⁷. It appears that the initial retention is free from isotope effect though their formation involves different recoil energies. Saito *et al.*¹⁰ observed the same retention in sodium bromate following (n, γ) reaction and ($n, 2n$) reaction in which the outgoing two

10. N. Saito, F. Ambe and H. Sano, *Nature*, 1965, **205**, 688.

neutrons impart far larger recoil energy to the atom than the gamma photon emitted in (n, γ) reaction.

A finding in accordance with the earlier work on sodium bromate system is that a linear relationship is obtained between the change in retention $\Delta R_0 (= R_\infty - R_0)$ (where R_∞ is the pseudo plateau retention observed at a particular temperature and R_0 is the retention at room temperature) and the reciprocal of the absolute temperature of annealing in both the forms of calcium bromate (Fig. 2). By extrapolation to the temperature axis, the threshold annealing temperature is found to be 85.5° . As the extent and rate of isothermal annealing is almost same for both the forms of calcium bromate, the same value of threshold annealing temperature is obtained. Our value of starting annealing temperature agrees very well with the value (85°) reported in the same system by Maddock and Müller⁷.

The isothermal annealing is explained by applying a classical treatment, similar to the one followed in our earlier communication¹¹, considering the decrease in the concentration of the radiofragments which are yet destined to anneal with time, $\Delta R_t = (R_\infty - R_t)$, where R_t is the retention of ^{80m}Br at time t , at a particular temperature. Fig. 3 shows the variation of logarithm of the fraction destined to anneal with time at 125° and 175° in dehydrated calcium bromate, the linear relationship denotes formally first order kinetics. The apparent first order rate constants at 125° and 175° are found to be 2.6 and $4.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation energy calculated from these rate constants is found to be 2.7 kcal/mole . As the rate of annealing in hydrated and dehydrated calcium bromate is almost the same, it can be assumed that the same value of activation energy holds good for both the systems.

Khare and Mohanty¹² reported that the kinetics of the annealing in γ -irradiated potassium bromate could be represented by the combination of a unimolecular and bimolecular processes. But the contribution of the second order process appears to be very small in the present system as the annealing proceeds only for 3 hrs, while in γ -irradiated potassium bromate it was continued upto 50 hrs. By neglecting the small contribution of the second order process, the conclusion can be drawn that the kinetics of annealing in calcium bromate system is of the first order which involves reformation of the close spaced fragments in a chemically damaged region.

Surprisingly enough in the present system there is no effect of phase transformation due to the loss of water of crystallization in contrast to other systems including other bromates studied by us¹³ and by earlier workers^{7,8}. It has been reported that the isothermal annealing ceases once the phase transformation is complete. However, in the present system it continues even after complete dehydration had taken place at 120°. In the absence of precise knowledge about the crystal structure of calcium bromate, it is not possible to explain these results.

The position of water molecule in the crystal matrix of calcium bromate may be such that it is not able to trap the radiolytic oxygen unlike in hydrated cadmium bromate⁹. The escape of oxygen or its getting trapped at sites inaccessible to the bromine fragments results in lowering the retention, as observed.

Department of Chemistry,
University of Poona,
Poona-7.

Received June 11, 1968
Revised MSS received February 25, 1971

12. M. Khare and S. R. Mohanty, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1527.
13. S. F. Patil, A Thesis submitted to the University of Poona (1971).